

Social media use for diversified farm businesses in Scotland: good practice guide

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Purpose of Guide:

This document provides good practice principles for social media platforms for diversified farm businesses in Scotland.

Diversified farm businesses can use social media platforms to reach new markets, sell more products and services, and build professional networks. At present, many diversified farm businesses (as with other types of rural businesses) are not engaging with social media or struggling to engage in an effective way. Other diversified farm businesses are successfully embracing social media platforms for a range of beneficial purposes. Various approaches can be found including sharing visual (both photo- and video-based) and text-based content illustrating the products and services offered.

This guide has been developed from research findings from the James Hutton Institute as part of the Scottish Government's Rural and Environmental Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS) under Topic B3: Improving Agricultural Practice (2022-2027). The views expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Scottish Government.

The guide has been designed around **six good practice** principles that are summarised in the table of contents.

Terminology:

Algorithm: The set of rules a social media platform uses to determine which content is shown to users in their feed.

Bots: A social media bot, short for social media robot, is an automated program or script designed to perform tasks on social media platforms. These tasks can range from simple actions like posting content, liking posts, and being fake accounts, to more complex interactions such as engaging in conversations or following users.

Followers: Users who subscribe to another user's content and updates on a social media platform.

Handle (username): A user's account name on social media platforms, often preceded by the "@" symbol.

Hashtag (#): A word or phrase preceded by the pound sign (#) used to categorize and organize content. Hashtags make it easier for users to discover posts on a specific topic.

Impressions: The total number of times a piece of content is displayed, whether clicked or not.

Influencer: A person with a significant and engaged following on social media who can influence their audience's opinions and behaviours.

Post: A short type of content or message that the user publishes. It takes several forms from mixing text, images, videos, links, and audio files.

Reach: The total number of unique users (first time seeing the post) who see a piece of content.

Reels: Short, multi-clip videos usually set to music (usually permanent post). Users can add various creative elements like text, stickers, and effects.

Stories: Short-lived, temporary content that disappears after a set period, commonly used on platforms like Instagram, Snapchat, and Facebook.

Troll: A social media troll is an individual who engages in online behaviour with the primary goal of provoking and upsetting others.

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1. Summary

This good practice guide has been produced from the results of research carried out at the James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, on the role of social media platforms for diversified farm businesses in Scotland, in 2021. The research was funded by the Scottish Government RESAS programme. Through netnographic (online ethnographic) research, diversified farm businesses and their use of social media was explored across several social media platforms. The research identified a number of ways in which social media can be used by diversified farm businesses as well as a number of principles that businesses can follow for the most effective use of these platforms. These principles are outlined in this document. Although the document is aimed primarily at diversified farm businesses (given that our research was specifically focused on these), the guidance can also be used by other types of rural businesses looking to engage with social media platforms.

Diversified farm businesses can use social media platforms to reach new markets, sell more products and services and build their professional networks. Many diversified farm businesses are **successfully embracing social media platforms** for a range of beneficial purposes. At the same time, other diversified farm businesses (as with other types of rural businesses) are not engaging with social media or struggling to engage in an effective way.

Various approaches are taken to the use of social media amongst diversified farm businesses. These include sharing visual (both photo- and video-based) and text-based content illustrating the products and services offered, across a number of social media applications. The most successful farm diversification accounts (in terms of numbers of followers) are taking various steps to increase their visibility. Smaller and newer accounts have had less time to develop a strategy, typically posting less frequently and using fewer platform functions. **Effective use of social media for diversified farm businesses** includes:

1. Determining which social media platform is appropriate for you.
2. **Posting regularly** (often daily).
3. Using a **range of content** types.
4. Using multiple **popular hashtags**.
5. **Telling an engaging story** about the diversified farm business including life on the farm.
6. Posting **attractive visual content**.
7. **Engaging actively** with other relevant (including local) businesses and promoting them on the platform.

Farmers face several **barriers to engagement**:

1. **Digital connectivity issues** are prevalent in many rural areas.
2. **Low levels of digital skills** can be an issue, as well as a lack of confidence or awareness of the different tools available.
3. **Farmers are busy**, especially those diversifying into multiple revenue streams. This leaves little time for the development of the skills necessary for effective social media use.
4. There is an **overwhelming choice** of social media (and other digital) platforms, which are perceived to change too frequently in terms of rules and functionality.

Effective management of social media use is important, so that it does not become too time-consuming and detract from important on-farm work. Strategies for effective time management include:

1. Plan social media time carefully, using off-peak times (e.g. in the evenings) when work is not required on the farm.
2. Developing a strategy of content types and approaches, including time allocations for social media, times for posting, and which social media platforms to focus on.
3. Scheduling content using in-app functionality in the relevant social media platforms, or third party apps such as Hootsuite.

Good Practice Principle 1: Identify which social media platform(s) to focus on.

The choice of platforms to engage with is often overwhelming for small businesses. Social media channels can provide similar functions to one another, but they are also all slightly different. For example, whilst LinkedIn is primarily a tool for **building professional networks**, Instagram and Facebook provide platforms for **reaching diverse audiences** (with Instagram being the more visual of the two platforms, though this is gradually changing).

This makes Instagram and Facebook useful tools for **digital marketing**. Twitter can be used in this way too, though businesses often use Twitter for professional networking and **raising awareness about specific issues**. Snapchat and WhatsApp are useful communication tools which can be used for **building groups of interest**. New platforms are emerging all the time, though they generally take time to gain critical mass (and there is no guarantee that a new social media platform will gain enough traction to be a valuable investment of your time in its early stages of release).

Take the time to familiarise yourself with social media platforms, their functions, and ways of working, look for good practice examples of social media accounts who are doing similar work to your own. You will soon determine which platform feels like a good “fit” for whichever aspect of farming or diversification activities that you are keen to share with a wider audience.

Good Practice Principle 2: Familiarise yourself with the different functions of the platform(s).

Social media platforms boast different functions (though there is a good deal of crossover). For example, in the case of Instagram, a range of functions are offered. Regular **posts** appear on a user's feed as well as the account holder's "grid" and are organised in a user's feed according to the algorithm.

These feed **posts** can take several different formats – static photograph **posts**, "carousels" (multiple photos in one **post**) and **videos** (in the form of "Reels" which might feature a voiceover or be accompanied by music which is added to the **video**). Content can also be shared with users via **Stories** function. **Stories** can be added in various formats – photo or **video** with voiceover (or with music added from Instagram's extensive library), resharing of one's own and other people's **posts**, linking to websites and other online content external to the Instagram app, and so on. There is also a function by which users can share live **video** – either on their own or in collaboration with other accounts, which is used to engage followers who are able to ask questions in the chat function during these live events. In addition to these different forms of content there are multiple ways of engaging with followers and other users of the app.

For example, when creating a **reel** or photo **post**, a common practice is to use **hashtags (#)** which make the content visible to a wider audience based on shared interests. Another practice is to tag other accounts in your (place-based or online) community in order to support their work, ask their advice, credit their ideas and so on. These actions help social media users to build their online community, share their content and connect with a wider audience. Some of these functionalities, such as hashtags and **stories**, are common across multiple platforms.

#SHEEP

#FARM

#SALE

#FEED

Good Practice Principle 3: create engaging content and build your following.

Diversified farm businesses have a range of content types to share, including posts about business services and products, links to and information about events and workshops, personal family photos, photos of and information about the team behind the farm, the rural landscape within which the farm is situated, interiors and exteriors of agritourism accommodation, resharing photos and reviews by guests or customers, and so on. The imagery of beautiful outdoor rural settings and seasonal aspects (e.g. Autumn leaves) can be used to attract engagement with posts.

Photos and videos serve several functions. They can **tell a story about your business including the services or products on offer and help to create a brand identity** that seeks to attract potential new customers and retain existing ones. Regarding the content type, you might choose to focus on diversified products or services, or more on the working farm itself, which might function as a more indirect form of marketing through **storytelling**. Some farm businesses have even created “farm characters” that regularly feature in their feeds – typically a farm animal acting as a mascot for the farm- to encourage followers to check in on the account frequently. Other strategies include running giveaways (often in collaboration with other relevant businesses) to draw in new followers and engagement as well as posting questions to encourage followers to engage directly with feed posts and stories.

Success on social media is subjective and there are different ways in which an account can be considered successful. One of these might be the size of an account’s following (even though it is worth remembering that not all followers will become customers). For diversified farm businesses, a larger following means a larger potential market as well as being more visible to potential collaborators and organisations who might provide support and exposure. Therefore, it is good practice to actively strive to increase the number of followers on social media platforms.

The most easily found (or visible) diversified farm businesses on social media platforms tend to be the ones which are using the platforms most frequently and diversely. Social media content is generally organised by algorithms which favour more popular content, and which drive content to users based on perceived preferences and existing connections. This means that there is a somewhat unfortunate “Catch 22” in that the larger accounts tend to be given more exposure by the algorithm within each of the platforms. However, there are a number of steps that you can take to increase your visibility:

1. **Post regularly** (often daily).
2. Use a **range of content** types, and embrace new functions introduced by the platforms.
3. Use multiple **popular hashtags**.
4. **Tell an engaging story** about the diversified farm business including life on the farm.
5. Post **attractive visual content**.
6. **Engage actively** with potential customers and other relevant (including local) businesses including by promoting them on the platform.

It is worth noting that, although posting regularly across multiple platforms seems to be an effective way to reach more followers and engage more potential customers on social media, this might not be an easy strategy for all businesses, especially if you are time poor. The next section presents guidance on how to effectively manage time spent on social media.

Good Practice Principle 4:

Time allocation - More time on the farm, less time in the office.

The farmers' priority is business and farming is demanding which requires a lot of time and energy, especially for those farmers diversifying into multiple revenue streams. This leaves little time for developing the skills necessary for effective social media use and keeping up to date with new Apps. The key is to **use off-peak times**, i.e., evenings after work, bad weather days and low-priority times, this requires finding the balance that works for schedules and priorities.

How much time you should allocate each week will be determined by your **social media goals**:

- Growing your audience and consumer reach.
- Making the market more aware of your brand or farm product range.
- Increase traffic to your website or farmstall.
- Improving networking with the community or other farmers.
- Increasing sales and enquiries.
- Educating people about your farm produce and farm production.

The social media strategy could be a **variety and spread of posts**, here is an example of a farm social media posting strategy, your own strategy will depend upon your own goals in using social media:

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What are your farm diversification Social Media goals?

Good Practice Principle 5:

Using Scheduling Tools – let the AI tools work for you.

Farmers are busy, especially those diversifying into multiple revenue streams. Marketing is often the last priority because essential tasks such as feeding animals, welcoming guests, or dealing with customers can take priority. This can mean little time to develop the digital skills and knowledge necessary for using social media and other digital platforms. The most easily found farm businesses on social media platforms tend to use the platforms most frequently and diversely. However, there are several steps that successful accounts are taking to increase their visibility. These accounts are typically posting most frequently on more platforms, and using the full range of functions that the platforms offer, quickly embracing new functions introduced by the platforms. This regular posting could be assisted by automation. **Social media automation tools** can help schedule posts and manage interactions. Automation (performing posts automatically without user assistance) can be timesaving, but it must be balanced with real-time interaction to preserve authenticity.

In other words, a farmer can create seven posts with photos to be sent automatically one each day at 10 am. Choosing the time to launch these posts automatically will depend on your audience. If your posts are geared to the farming community, your post should be set to post later when the working day is finished. Certain strategies might be useful to those with less time, such as using functions which allow social media users to post the same content across multiple platforms (available within the apps themselves as well as via third-party apps which are aimed at organising social media content over multiple platforms, such as Hootsuite). The third-party apps also will evolve with changing online updates and changes.

Good Practice Principle 6:

Managing comments and replies

Managing customer comments and replying to questions can be time-consuming. Here are some guidelines for time management in this area:

- **Regular Monitoring:**
Regularly monitor your social media channels for new comments and replies. This allows you to address any issues promptly and engage with your audience in a timely manner. Set a time for this daily and avoid getting distracted by every notification.
- **Be Professional and Positive:**
Keep your responses professional, even when faced with negative comments. Avoid engaging in arguments and maintain a positive tone. Remember there are online trolls that intend to provoke and upset others.
- **Address Concerns Privately:**
Consider addressing a specific issue or complaint privately through direct messages or emails if a user has a specific issue or complaint. This prevents potential public escalation.
- **Monitor Analytics (user participation):**
Use analytics tools to track the performance of your social media engagement. This can help you understand what types of content generate more engagement and adjust your strategy accordingly. In other words, what post created the most likes and comments?

is when people share your post with others. There are no shares for this post</p> <p>Each post can be compared with other posts to see what has been the most popular on your social media platform. These analytics help give you an idea of what your followers enjoy.</p>	
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Further Reading:

Creating a Social Media Marketing Strategy for Your Farm Market

<https://extension.psu.edu/creating-a-social-media-marketing-strategy-for-your-farm-market>

How farmers use social media to tackle rural isolation and educate the public

<https://mark-making.com/farmers-use-social-media-tackle-rural-isolation-educate-public/>

Tweeting from the Tractor – 7 Secrets to Successful Social Media Farming

<https://www.convinceandconvert.com/social-media/7-secrets-to-successful-social-media-farming/>

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